

Design of Kinetic Building Envelope of a High-performing Building using BIM

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Abstract

Buildings are significant contributors to global energy consumption. Envelopes are the boundary between the interior and exterior environment and are of vital importance to energy control and occupant comfort. Traditional static facades are not the best energy conservers when it comes to changing conditions. In response to this kinetic facade system offer a much more active approach. This thesis explores the development of kinetic envelop systems through the use of BIM tools to determine how such systems could improve building performance and sustainability. The idea is to use BIM workflows combined with parametric design tools to create a kinetic facade that responds dynamically to environmental conditions.

A base-case office building model was developed, and then kinetic façade panels were designed that would move in real time as the position of the sun changed during the course of the day and the seasons. Its performance was tested by simulating it and comparing it to static facade systems. The analysis demonstrates that the kinetic system performed better than static systems by reducing solar radiation exposure during peak hours. Additionally, one of the

key advantages of the study was the ability to visualize façade performance. This provided an immersive experience that could simulate real-world occupant conditions. The visual response shows how kinetic facades can enhance environmental control and user comfort. The research concludes that kinetic façade systems, when integrated with BIM workflows, offer significant potential for sustainable building design. Future research should include more environmental parameters and also look into occupant-controlled systems in order to make kinetic facades more adaptable and efficient.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/r0vxVE00rvU>

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